

Cadmium sequestration through the pseudomorphic replacement of CaCO₃ by hydroxylapatite in phosphate solutions.

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Phosphate and cadmium water contamination caused by the overuse of fertilizers and other anthropogenic activities has become a concern in many areas throughout the last decades. These toxic elements concentrate in the soil and water and accumulate in the crops, entering the food chain and potentially leading to the contamination of the population of the concerned areas. Various minerals have been studied for cadmium capture from solution through mineralization and/or adsorption processes at mineral-fluid interfaces and both calcium carbonate and apatite have shown good uptake capacities toward this element. Furthermore, calcium carbonate minerals can be replaced pseudomorphically by apatite through a coupled dissolution-precipitation mechanism when immersed in a solution containing phosphate [1]. Hence, the combination of both previously mentioned reactions could be used for water decontamination. Here, we report on the efficiency and mechanism of cadmium capture from solution during the replacement reaction of Carrara marble by hydroxyapatite [2]. Cubes of Carrara marble have been reacted in sealed hydrothermal reactors at 200°C in solutions containing various concentrations of phosphate and cadmium for times between 4 and 60 days. The samples were then sectioned and analysed by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), BackScattered Electron (BSE) imaging, Electron Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS), Microprobe and Raman Spectroscopy. The nanoscale reaction at the sample surface has been observed with in-situ Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) in fluid flow and static solutions on the (10-14) surface of freshly cleaved calcite. The coupled dissolution-precipitation reaction observed and the capture of cadmium by the newly formed phase as well as a comparison of the mechanism efficiency for Cd capture with other materials will be presented.

[1] Pedrosa, E.T., Putnis, C.V., and Putnis, A. (2016) The pseudomorphic replacement of marble by apatite: The role of fluid composition. *Chemical Geology*. 425 1–11.

[2] Wang, M., Wu, S., Guo, J., Zhang, X., Yang, Y., Chen, F., et al. (2019) Immobilization of cadmium by hydroxyapatite converted from microbial precipitated calcite. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*. 366 684–693.

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